

Attachment to the Study Report:

Questionnaire Script – Interviews on Marine Governance on Ovalau Island, Fiji, 2025

1. What happened during Cyclone Winston that led to the sandbank forming? How and why was it decided to be a *tabu* area? Can you share a story about this event? Can you share the status of the reefs before and after the cyclone?
2. Why was Nuku Cere chosen? Why did the village decide on the Tabu? Was its location near the reef passage important? Were other sites considered?
3. Were there discussions about establishing tabu areas in this qoliqoli¹ before Cyclone Winston, either here or in other nearby fishing grounds? Were there Tabu areas in nearby fishing grounds? What are some things that you have learned about that event?
4. In what year was the Tabu declared? How did the community hear about it—meeting, church, or chiefs? Was everyone informed at the same time?
5. Who first suggested the Tabu? What important decisions are made and by whom? What roles did the chief and the leaders of the clan play? How did the women and the youth take part in the decision making?
6. What type of Tabu is Nuku Cere considered? Is it closed forever or sometimes? Are there times when it can only be opened for harvest? Are there any fishing methods allowed when it is periodically opened?
7. How is the Tabu enforced? Who makes sure that the Tabu is respected? How do they check if the people follow the rules? What happens if someone breaks the Tabu?
8. Before the Tabu, who fished in that area? Men, women or both and how did the fishing practice changed afterwards?
9. Were all the community members supportive of the Tabu area? If not, who resisted and why? How were the disagreements handled?
10. Did the NGOs or the government play any part in the Tabu? Did they promise money, equipment or training? Was the support delivered? What was the objective behind the initiative? Do you think those objectives are working? If not then why?
11. Was there a ceremony to mark the Tabu? Who organized it? What was done during the ceremony?
12. Has the Tabu affected boat traffic or daily life in Vatukalo, and how has it affected your daily life? How do you perceive these changes? Is it good or bad?

¹ term for fishing grounds

13. What happens if someone breaks the tabu? Are punishments different for villagers compared to outsiders (People from Suva or village fishermen from Tailevu)? Who decides the penalty for the punishment?
14. Are there occasions when the tabu is temporarily lifted for harvests, and if so, what restrictions apply to species or methods? If yes then who can fish in this area? How long it is temporarily lifted? How many days? What species or fishing methods are allowed then?
15. Was there a last time when the Tabu area opened? Can you describe it?
16. How do villagers currently evaluate the tabu's effectiveness—have fish stocks or coral health improved, and should the tabu be extended or ended?
17. Is there any other activity that takes place near the Tabu areas perhaps on the reef passages (Waitovu and Toki)?
18. What was the health status of the coral before the creation of the Tabu area? Has coral health changed? Positive or Negative?
19. What is the agreed duration of the tabu, and how are decisions made about its continuation or closure? How long was the tabu meant to last? What is the process if it continues or closes? How are those decisions made?
20. How has the tabu area influenced the daily roles of women and men in marine resource use? Has it affected the way they earn income?
21. Are there any committees in Vatukalo (e.g., development, fisheries, church, women's, youth)? Is so who is part of that committee and what kind of issues do they handle, did they part take in any projects with NGOs?